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MEASURES FOR THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HISTORICAL SQUARES OF THE CITY OF SAMARKAND

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Abstract: This article presents a general description and the current state of the historical squares of Samarkand, the architectural, historical and functional role of squares in the city. The issues of the functional type of Samarkand districts and the connection of territories with streets, ensuring compositional harmony with the modern environment, as well as the introduction of capital repair methods are considered. The classification of all the territories of Samarkand by functional types and purpose, current state is carried out.

Based on this, the fields in each typological group were selected based on the possibilities of preservation. When placing structures on the central square, great importance is attached to its architectural composition. Buildings, structures and other elements placed on the square harmoniously combine with each other and complement each other, forming a kind of architectural ensemble. The article highlights the procedure for the full use of architectural composition techniques in the arrangement of the central square.

Keywords: Square, architecture, urban planning, madrasah, central square, modern urban planning, functional center, historical cities, compositional harmony, administrative buildings, public buildings, street, main square.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Samarqand tarixiy maydonlarining umumiy tavsifi va hozirgi holati, shahardagi maydonlarning me'moriy, tarixiy va funksional roli keltirilgan. Samarqand tumanlarining funksional turi va hududlarni ko'chalar bilan birlashtirish, zamonaviy muhit bilan kompozitsion uyg'unlikni ta'minlash, shuningdek, kapital ta'mirlash usullarini joriy etish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Samarqandning barcha hududlari funksional turlari va maqsadi, hozirgi holati bo'yicha tasniflandi. Shunga asoslanib, har bir tipologik guruhdagi maydonlar saqlash imkoniyatlari asosida tanlangan.

Inshootlarni Markaziy maydonga joylashtirishda uning me'moriy tarkibiga katta ahamiyat beriladi. Maydonda joylashgan binolar, inshootlar va boshqa elementlar bir-biri bilan uyg'unlashib, bir-birini to'ldirib, o'ziga xos me'moriy ansamblni tashkil etadi. Maqolada Markaziy maydonni tartibga solishda me'moriy kompozitsiya texnikasidan to'liq foydalanish tartibi yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Maydon, arxitektura, shaharsozlik, madrasa, markaziy maydon, zamonaviy shaharsozlik, funksional markaz, tarixiy shaharlar, kompozitsion uyg'unlik, ma'muriy binolar, jamoat binolari, ko'cha, bosh maydon.

Introduction. The reconstruction of historical cities and their squares and centers requires a differentiated approach depending on the historical-urban planning value and the degree of influence of existing architectural monuments in the city on them not only on different cities, but also on different areas within the same city limits. In modern urban planning practice, the stratification of historical urban areas is carried out by determining the different order of restoration. It is recommended to consider a number of common issues regarding areas of historical importance, including "orderly" territorialization issues, before moving on to the tasks of revitalizing the center of small and medium-sized historic cities.

The squares of the city of Turkey were partially, and the main functional center of the city was the Square and markets were located inside it. He practically shirdi different trading or service processes with benefits, balkim sometimes artisans developed their own products. For example, blacksmiths made axes and were sold on the market.

The classification of all regions of Samarkand according to their functional types and purposes, as it is now, was carried out. It follows that the fields in each typological group are selected based on conservation capabilities. The construction of the protection gods

must be subject to the protection of monuments and the inherent requirements of the territory. The main task of the gods of strict construction regulation is to preserve the general character and individual details of the historically formed urban environment, ensuring the conditions of view of the protected object from a considerable distance. Separate Level 2 objects of historical-artistic value within the boundaries of this zone also belong to detection and study. New construction can be carried out on the territory of the zone, but it must be subject to the requirements of its planned solutions and height, composition of the building, landscaping and landscaping.

Materials and methods. The square it is an open space surrounded by buildings, structures or trees, which in the past had lavish courtyard spaces in Assyria, Babylon, Ancient Egypt as part of a complex of palaces and temples. Their architectural traditions were called by the Greeks-agara and the ancient Romans from dab. Between the 12th and 14th centuries, trading areas in European cities were considered the main territory. Squares were of great importance in the life of the city, proclamations and ordinances were read to the people gathered in the square.

Central Asian cities of the XIV-XVI centuries. There was a lively trade here. The choir stands out for its

unique urban layout. The squares are connected by streets located along the axis of the entrance street with the central square. One side of the other streets touches the square.

The Shape of the squares can vary depending on the terrain of the place, The Shape of the objects to be built and the connection with the streets. The width of the field is relative to the length 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 the best of these is 1: 1.6.

Buildings, structures are built on all sides of an indoor area, it is called an outdoor area if one side is focused on a lake, a pool, landscaped areas. On the central square, structures will be built that meet the demand of this place-a club, an administrative building, a shopping center, a kitchen, a tea room.[1]

When the structures are placed in the Central Square, importance is given to its architectural composition. The buildings, structures and other elements placed in the square harmonize with each other, complementing each other and forming a unique architectural ensemble. The methods of architectural composition are fully used in the organization of the central square. The work of the projects of the protection gods and construction regulatory zones is based on thorough historical-urban planning research. The purpose of these studies-to determine the historical and cultural characteristics of the city and its immediate surroundings, evaluate them and classify them in a number of signs, as well as clarify the requirements of the city for the protection of historical - architectural, archaeological monuments and other assets, studies can be complicated as a whole. it is divided into two parts: the first, the subject of the second part of the study, involves the analysis of the existing urban planning situation, aesthetic assessment of the landscape and the study of the composition of urban planning.

Results. Area conservation zones and regulatory landscape zones are defined as out-of-town obsolete nature conservation and regulation zones. For example, in the Khiva zoning scheme, it can be seen that this zone is far from the outskirts of the city. Most of the work dedicated to the restoration of the Centers of historical cities is somehow devoted to the interaction of residential and public buildings, the spatial organization of the building floor and the types of new residential buildings. In the process of implementing projects, the issue of the construction of low-rise residential buildings in the central zones, where restoration work is often necessary, is a special problem.

The central square of the cities are their visit cards and are the most basic places in the city. From the point of view of urban planning, this is considered the core of the city. From a social point of view, it attracts a large number of people and tourists, like local residents. Important events and celebrations will certainly take place here. The city square should be an important object with special attention in the design of the urban environment. The most important thing should be a natural place for the main buildings, a place for mass

gatherings, celebrations and events. Fields are divided into several types, depending on their formation.

Wide area. A building raised above the square must have dimensions that correspond to the place that represents it. In this case, the area will prevail in the building, the length of which will be much larger than the height of the building.

Core area. The space is formed around the center. **Grouped area.** Spatial units are combined into larger compositions.[2] Fields are divided into several types, depending on the purpose. One of the pressing issues that arise in the development of historical projects of neighborhoods is, on the one hand, the strict condition for the preservation of monuments, and on the other hand, the solution of the productive use of architectural monuments as a means of the development of urban social tasks that are very effective in small cities.

Main fields. Here festivals and people in the city meet and relax. Traffic and pedestrian flow will be higher. As a rule, such squares will be adjacent to the main streets or located in their quarter. In and around the main square of the city will be located objects of public and entrepreneurial infrastructure of urban importance-houses of culture and Recreation, concert halls, museums, etc. The perimeter of the main square, as a rule, forms an object of public and entrepreneurial infrastructure, as well as secondary streets of main city and district significance. The intensity of traffic and pedestrian flow in the Square is high, and parking is usually not organized, since this prevents the movement of pedestrians and vehicles.

Transportation area-traffic flows are distributed to The approached streets. In the Transport area, the intensity of parking and pedestrian flow will be high. In the Transport area, there will be rooms, pavilions, kiosks where trade and service facilities are installed. Parking lots and public transport stops will be available within the boundaries of the square. Transport areas as a rule, the main transport nodes are adjacent to railways or bus stations, providing communication with neighboring cities. Within their borders there are parking lots and public transport stops. The dimensions of these squares are determined by the intensity of traffic and the number of streets that cross the square [4]. Organization of movement in the field should not be lost for aesthetic reasons.

Market Square. The Market Square is an area designed for market transfer trading. It is an important feature of many cities around the world. A Market Square is an open space where department stores are traditionally set up to trade, usually a specific day of the week, known as market day. The market area consists of a square or quadrangle, or sometimes just an extension of the main street. It is usually located in the city center and will be surrounded by large buildings such as the city hall, important shops and hotels, a post office, small shops and commercial buildings.

Multifunctional space-the role of the Square in the urban sphere and the work it performs are determined in the general sphere. When designing the square, it is necessary to draw up a scheme for organizing traffic and pedestrian traffic.

Street, Square-common use areas bounded by the red lines of the city's Street-road network [4].

Another type of Square is the unloading area for intra-city traffic. In old cities, intersecting streets in different corners often cause inconveniences for high-speed motor transport at intersections, and this requires the creation of a special type of space, which is called a dynamic type at intersections.

The third type of squares in a modern city should be those that children can gather and spend in outdoor games, where when crossing streets they should not pose a danger to children. Boulevards can play the same role.

Discussion. According to the architectural and compositional methods of organization and development, the territory is divided into closed, semi-closed and open areas. In closed areas, the surrounding buildings will be of decisive importance. Semi-enclosed spaces would have formed large public buildings on one side. More parks and gardens, water structures play an important role in the composition in open spaces [3].

The main purpose of the developed project proposals and principles:

Return to the pedestrian area;

- Restoration of the lost traditional architectural and landscape pattern and irrigation system;
- to create places on their territory that meet the requirements of territorial climatic conditions for the rest and recreation of guests, as well as comfort and service conditions.

The combination of the proposed repair methods and principles allows you to eventually transfer a certain territory from one type to another, that is, to restore the main functional purpose envisaged by the authors.

The following methods and techniques were used to solve the assigned tasks:

1. practical study of objects and recording the use of the " fields " environment, which are studied at different times of the day;
2. Observation of pedestrian and traffic flows, their distribution.
3. Search, analysis and comparison of graphic materials - schemes, plans, drawings, engravings, photographs of different years, text documents describing the location of the areas under consideration and revealing their peculiarities; comparing them with modern design proposals.[6]

Administrative and collective centers in the cities of Uzbekistan include regional, municipal buildings, farm buildings, Treasury buildings and other departments. In addition, buildings of cultural and educational importance (theaters, cinemas, biblioteka, clubs, museums) and shopping complexes can be placed in the city center. On the other hand, it is possible to choose

one of the cities as a universal administrative center in non-large settlements.

It is determined by the fact that in the repair and restoration of the historically built central squares in the city of Samarkand, based on modern urban planning, it is possible to ensure compositional harmony from the current Muhid and popularize the main repair methods used. The practical significance of the research results is that in the development of proposals and recommendations for a project to update and restore the functions of the central squares in the city of Samarkand, they can be used in practice to expand and improve the ways of future development of the field of architecture and urban planning of the city of Samarkand.

Conclusion. The practical significance of the research results lies in the fact that the graphical method of covering proposed and tested plans with a computer can be used not only in the reconstruction and restoration of "fields", but also in the conditions of updating historical environments, planning their development. This method can be used in striking new, little-studied existing "environmental architectonic "fields" in the environment and in the modern urban planning system, identifying their functions.

The development of the general plans of the historical city of Uzbekistan is primarily to take care of cultural monuments. The historic city core, three main landmarks are highlighted in the preservation and restoration of the central squares:

- maintaining the role and importance of the idea of field composition;
- restoration and improvement of residential areas ;
- adaptation of the street network to the requirements of the city.

The open architectural spaces of the urban environment are the most important structural elements of modern cities. To reveal the unique aesthetic image of the city, it is not enough to have unique public, residential and industrial buildings, both historical and modern. Streets and squares are a real scene of urban life, where various events are held. In the course of the construction of the city, along with historical squares, modern squares also appear. They have different functional purposes and often combine several functions-business, trade, leisure, architectural, etc. Any sphere has a certain compositional structure that establishes an emotional and aesthetic relationship between all space planning components and affects a person. According to the principles of further development and renewal of areas and the prospects for their development, methods of improvement on each type are justified. These proposals and styles were created both for squares in the historical environment and for squares in the new part of the city, for all types of squares that have undergone significant changes since their appearance.

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